

Implementation of CORSA on Nvidia Jetson Hardware

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INTRODUCTION

The rate at which remote sensing information is being captured by far outpaces the rate at which it may be downlinked from space. This holds particularly true for hyperspectral sensors, which need to downlink 12 to 16 bit hypercubes of up to 200 bands. As an example, CSIMBA, the hyperspectral sensor of the IPERLITE mission from AeroSpaceLab scheduled to be launched in 2025, produces an average of over 5 TB per day but can only downlink an average of under 20 GB per day without extra allotted budget; resulting in a discrepancy of a factor of 256. The downlink bottleneck, which presents a hinderance to the space industry by itself, additionally greatly limits the development and accessibility of hyperspectral applications. This reality has spurred much research into compression algorithms using all kinds of techniques, including neural networks (NNs).

The usage of NNs for the purpose of data compression has been attested to the late 1980s [1], but arguably the first deep generative data models for data compression appear in 2016 [2]. There are two categories of compression: lossless and lossy. Lossless compression is possible with neural networks but does not achieve compression ratios sufficient to tackle the onslaught of data generation we experience today. Hence, most applied research tackles neural lossy compression. Among them, Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Transformers are particularly well-represented in the literature. CORSA, our model we have implemented on hardware, is one such case: a VAE with CNNs or a Transformer-based backbone.

Up until a few years ago, running NNs in space was a rare occurrence due to their computational complexity, but a new generation of hardware might make the usage of NNs in space viable. Indeed, Spiral Blue launched a satellite with a Jetson Xavier component in space only last year [3] and has already received transmissions. We have therefore chosen the next generation of hardware, the Nvidia Jetson Orin NX 16GB as the prototype for deployment of our CORSA model. This device is a System on Module (SoM) based on the GA10B GPU Ampere architecture GPU. It hosts eight Arm Cortex A78AE CPU and one thousand and twenty-four CUDA and thirty-two Tensor cores along with sixteen Gb of LPDDR5 memory.

We will start on an overview of the CORSA algorithm and its relevant capabilities, including comparisons to the CCSDS algorithm, and end with the implementation of one version of this algorithm on the Jetson Orin.

ON CORSA

Algorithm Overview

CORSA [4] has been first developed as an ESA PhiLab EO Science for Society project for both compression and as a multi-purpose backbone for AI-based application. Such backbones were later named foundation models, although they are usually larger than the ones we use, since we also target edge devices which would struggle to run most foundation models. The technology behind CORSA is a multi-level vector quantized variational auto-encoder (VQVAE), inspired by hierarchical generative VQVAE [5]. Most variants of CORSA include a convolutional two- or three-level backbone, but transformer-based architecture with masking strategies have also been successfully implemented [6].

The framework has demonstrated an ability for compression rivalling that of JPEG2000 in terms of degradation and compression power on Sentinel 2 (S2) RGBNIR imagery, the four bands which have a 10m resolution. The compression ratio (CR) achieved with CORSA is of around 20 for a Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) of around 50 if S2 imagery is assumed to be 14 bits and around 56 if S2 imagery is assumed to be 16 bits. The compression power is higher if all ten

S2 bands are compressed simultaneously. The same CORSA models have been shown to be useful foundation models for tasks such as super-resolved parcel delineation [4], flood detection [7], landcover classification and change detection [8].

On data sources such as S2, CORSA’s greatest asset lies in being a light-weight foundation model. Its compression capabilities largely depend on the compression potential of a given data source.

On Compression Potential

Not all data may be compressed equally; the maximum achievable compression ratio by the CORSA algorithm alone for a given reconstruction error varies from instrument to instrument. The CORSA algorithm leverages correlations. In other words, the more spectral and spatial correlations exist in a given dataset, the easier it becomes to achieve high compression ratio while maintaining near-lossless reconstruction. In the domain of Earth Observation, lower resolution data is more spatially correlated than high resolution data and hyperspectral data is more spectrally correlated than multispectral data.

The HyspecNet dataset [9], captured by the ENMAP instrument, comprises 80 channels in the [400-900]nm domain, which includes the visible spectrum and part of the near infrared before water vapor absorption spectral bands, and has a spatial resolution of 30m by pixel. As expected, the compression ratios achieved for ENMAP are far superior to those achieved on S2. To illustrate CORSA’s difference in compression and reconstruction power between both datasets, we have plotted them in “Fig. 1” against the CCSDS standard [10].

Figure 1: Comparisons between the CCSDS and CORSA algorithms relative to compression power and reconstruction accuracy.

We have used CCSDS with relative error and absolute error for this exercise, but not with both. The compression ratios are computed in different ways for the CSDSS algorithm and the CORSA algorithm due to their inherent differences in implementation. When using the CCSDS, a relative or absolute error (or both) is set beforehand and a compression ratio is estimated from the average of compression ratios obtained for each tile of the evaluation dataset. For CORSA, the compression ratio is set beforehand, and might only take certain discrete values since they are determined by the codebooks’ sizes. There is no cap on the absolute and relative errors due to the probabilistic nature of Artificial Intelligence (AI) models. For both algorithms, the quality metric PSNR is estimated across the evaluation dataset under the assumption that ENMAP and S2 data were captured in 16bit for both algorithms.

Achieving Near-Lossless Compression on Hyperspectral Data

For CORSA, high compression ratios may be achieved using one model even on hyperspectral data. However, when it comes to achieving near-lossless reconstruction, in other words near imperceptible loss in quality both according to appropriate metrics and the human eye upon reconstruction, one CORSA model proves insufficient due to constraints in data and size. Hence, for best-performing CORSA models in terms of reconstruction quality “Fig. 1”, we run three CORSA models in parallel to reconstruct the full spectrum. The ranges attributed to each model depend, again, on the correlations between the channels. Indeed, in the VNIR range, there are several breaks in correlation continuity outlining three domains, one for each model. These domains correspond to the violet-light red range (fifty-four channels), the red edge (fifteen channels) and the near infrared (eleven channels). Data in the red edge and near infrared are often more difficult to compress than those in the visible spectrum due to their larger distribution. The best model we have crafted for the HyspecNet dataset, offering a high compression ratio without compromising the quality of the reconstruction, is

comprised of three models and has a compression ratio of one hundred and sixteen, as shown in “Table 1”. It comes at a high computational cost however.

Table 1: List of CORSA models trained for the compression of ENMAP-like data. The PSNR is computed assuming the data is captured in 16bits.

# models	CR	PSNR	SAM	PSF	SSIM	# parameters(M)	MACs(G)
3	97	63.0	0.995	0.379	0.945	237.59	389.54
3	116	62.8	0.995	0.323	0.954	237.59	389.54
1	264	61.5	0.998	0.344	0.965	106.05	175.02
1	309	60.5	0.995	0.310	0.954	106.05	175.02
1	373	59.7	0.995	0.261	0.954	106.05	175.02

Moreover, the quality metrics such as PSNR, we use three other metrics to assess the reconstruction power of our models. The Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) measures the similarity of the spectral signal in the target and reconstructed image per pixel, which is relevant for many hyperspectral applications. The SAM is comprised between -1 and 1, and the higher the better. During all our experiments, SAM values rarely fall under 0.95, they are therefore not used for discriminating the models, but as information to hyperspectral domain experts. The Point-Spread-Function (PSF) measures the sharpness of the target compared to the reconstructed image, which factors in greatly into the visual quality of the image from a human standpoint. We compute the PSF function in two-dimensions, not one, and take the energy at the peak, therefore, our PSF value theoretically range from 0 to 1. In practice however, an image with a PSF of 0.28 is very sharp and nearly indistinguishable from the original. The Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) is a newer metric to assess the visual quality of an image and it also ranges from 0 to 1. Like for SAM, we consistently get very high values for the SSIM and do not use it as a discriminator for our models. It is presented for informational purposes.

Another way of achieving near-lossless reconstruction with CORSA, especially useful when training data is lacking, is transfer learning, which has been demonstrated to work between similar data sources such as ENMAP and PRISMA. Since we do not yet aim to enable training on-board, we will not elaborate on the topic further in this paper.

IMPLEMENTATION ON JETSON

To proceed with the implementation of a CORSA encoder on hardware, we have chosen two-level CORSA models with convolutional backbones trained to encode and decode ENMAP data in the violet-light red range. We have run the following test with different sizes of models as shown in “Table 2”. Note that the large model is the one used to tackle the violet-light red range in the optimal model collection we use to achieve compression ratios of 116 on the ENMAP data. We were pleased to discover that our model not only fit on the Jetson, but would also perform inference in a reasonable amount of time; although smaller is always better when it comes to edge applications.

Table 2: characteristics of deployed models

Model	# parameters(M)	MACs(G)
tiny	0.44	0.79
small	1.70	2.92
default	6.70	11.23
large	26.58	43.99

Embedded Deployment

The first step towards deployment is converting the CORSA pytorch encoder and decoder to a portable onnx format. The onnx encoder model is used as input for the TensorRT framework to create a device-optimized 'engine plan', using the trtexec tool [11] tool as part of the JetPack SDK [12]. It performs an on-device exhaustive search over the optimization parameters to find the best execution strategy for the model for throughput and accuracy. These automated optimizations involve layer fusion, kernel selection, and precision constraints.

The resulting execution engine is evaluated in terms of throughput and power consumption. Reconstruction quality is evaluated using the full precision FP32 decoder onnx model on PC. The throughput is measured for different batch sizes and power profiles.

The Jetson device allows for different power profiles to be set. These power profiles are defined by the minimum and maximum CPU and GPU clock speeds and active CPU cores, as shown in “Table 3”. The following standard profiles

were used and evaluated: 10W, 15W, 25W and MAXN. It is worth noting that these profiles are not a sustained power limit in our evaluation. Actual power consumption is measured at runtime using the on-device power monitor (tegrastats, as part of the JetPack SDK). Also note that the standard 25W profile has a lower GPU frequency than the 15W profile, but more active CPU cores.

Table 3: characteristics of default JetPack power profiles

Power Budget	10W	15W	25W	MAXN
CPU ONLINE	4	4	8	8
CPU MAX_FREQ	1190.4 MHz	1420.8 MHz	1497.6 MHz	1984 MHz
GPU MAX_FREQ	612 MHz	612 MHz	408 MHz	918 MHz

Inference Efficiency

Throughput, power consumption and efficiency are measured for each profile, each model with different batch sizes, in “Tables 4, 5 and 6”. Note that one image has a dimension of 128 by 128 and each pixel contains 54 channels. As the 10W/15W/25W profiles have similar GPU clocking speeds and the workload is mostly GPU bound, “Table 5” shows the power consumption is similar for these profiles. We have chosen to include the normalized mega-pixel per second per Watt (MPs/s/W) as it shows the efficiency of the model execution.

Table 4: Throughput measured in mega-pixels per second (MP/s)

Model	Batch size	10W	15W	25W	MAXN
tiny	1	6.01	6.07	6.21	11.8
	2	6.58	6.55	6.83	14.82
	4	6.93	6.91	7.58	16.36
	8	7.00	7.00	8.11	17.55
	16	7.07	7.07	8.28	18.11
small	1	4.92	4.92	4.96	10.42
	2	5.21	5.22	5.68	12.23
	4	5.55	5.55	6.47	13.92
	8	5.54	5.54	6.58	14.25
default	1	2.9	2.91	3.33	7.10
	2	3.06	3.06	3.57	7.71
	4	3.14	3.14	3.82	8.29
	8	3.15	3.15	3.89	8.58
large	1	1.2	1.2	1.49	3.24

Table 5: Power consumption measured during inference in Watts (W).

Model	Batch size	10W	15W	25W	MAXN
tiny	1	10.94	11.0	10.94	18.77
	2	12.23	12.27	12.33	23.91
	4	12.47	12.51	15.35	25.36
	8	11.84	11.96	12.37	24.32
	16	12.00	12.02	12.69	24.86
small	1	11.90	11.90	11.84	22.41
	2	12.41	12.39	12.67	24.92
	4	12.47	12.35	12.90	25.61
	8	12.45	12.51	15.83	26.34
default	1	12.08	12.12	12.47	24.92
	2	12.59	12.59	13.26	26.97
	4	12.51	12.47	13.48	27.41
	8	12.51	12.51	13.38	27.75
large	1	12.71	12.75	13.54	27.80

Table 6: normalized mega-pixels per second per Watt (MPs/s/W)

Model	Batch size	10W	15W	25W	MAXN
tiny	1	0.549	0.551	0.567	0.629
	2	0.538	0.534	0.554	0.620
	4	0.556	0.553	0.494	0.645
	8	0.591	0.585	0.656	0.722
	16	0.589	0.588	0.653	0.728
small	1	0.413	0.413	0.419	0.465
	2	0.420	0.422	0.448	0.491
	4	0.445	0.450	0.502	0.544
	8	0.445	0.443	0.416	0.541
default	1	0.240	0.240	0.267	0.285
	2	0.243	0.243	0.269	0.286
	4	0.251	0.252	0.283	0.303
	8	0.251	0.252	0.291	0.309
large	1	0.094	0.094	0.110	0.117

Inference Quality

Each model and their implementations have been evaluated on the same dataset as reported in “Table 7”. Note that the unexpected differences in performance between the small and default versions of the model might be attributed to chance. As mentioned earlier in the section, the model used as part of the best model collection for ENMAP data is the large version. A default, intuited to be the best fit for the hardware while offering a high reconstruction quality, a small and a tiny model were also trained three times for the sake of comparison. On average, the default model has outperformed the small model, but we have selected the best performing weights for each model size to implement on the hardware and the small model happened to have a particularly well-performing outlier.

“Figures 2,3,4,5 and 6” show an example of the reconstruction of a hyperspectral image after compression on the Jetson Orion using the TRT runtime. The images remain visually appealing and very little degradation is noticeable, save for the tiny model. Please note that the models are of different sizes but have all the same compression ratio, which is 275 on the violet to light red range.

Figure 2: Example of a target, all images are in false RGB colours

Figure 3: tiny model inference

Figure 4: small model inference

Figure 5: default model inference

Figure 6: large model inference

Table 7: Quality metrics for pytorch, onnx and trt implementations of each model

Model	TRT			ONNX			Torch		
	PSNR	PSF	SAM	PSNR	PSF	SAM	PSNR	PSF	SAM
tiny	56.5	0.184	0.983	55.5	0.179	0.980	55.5	0.179	0.980
small	60.2	0.222	0.999	63.2	0.229	0.999	63.2	0.229	0.999
default	60.2	0.224	0.999	62.9	0.230	0.999	62.9	0.230	0.999
large	59.4	0.253	0.998	63.9	0.259	0.999	63.9	0.259	0.999

The quality metrics above show that the performance reduction between the native pytorch implementation and the device optimized version of the network is small, meaning the CORSA model’s implementation on the NVIDIA Jetson is viable. Moreover, the values of MPs/s are high enough to open the possibility for real-time or real-near-time compression and semantic understanding, which is also part of CORSA capabilities as a foundation model, of hyperspectral data onboard. Such feat has, to the best of our knowledge, been attempted once in a drone [13] a few months ago and has not yet been implemented in space missions.

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

We were successful in porting our CORSA model onto the Jetson, which we believe is likely to be used in space missions in the future, bringing us one step closer to using CORSA as a compression model in space. There are still many optimizations and tracks left unexplored.

As far as optimizations go, we have at least three options we aim to assess in the future. So far, we have not yet made use of the Jetson’s Deep Learning Accelerator (DLA) cores. And, as of the time of writing of this paper, it is yet unclear how GPU-DLA synchronization will impact execution performance. A second possible further optimization that is the use of hardware accelerated fine-grained structured sparsity. A third optimization would be to target the size of the network itself. The deployment method presented here uses Post-Training Quantization (PTQ) to FP16 and TF32. We expect a possible improvement in both quality and performance by quantized aware retraining of the model to FP16 and/or INT8 precision. Moreover, the model has yet to be optimized for inference using pruning, which has been known to improve the generalisation capabilities of a model [14] while also reducing its size and inference time.

CORSA has been so far used for compression and as a foundation model on S2 data, for compression on hyperspectral data, and has the potential to be used for many more wavelengths and applications. We aim to diversify our S2-based applications to showcase the potential of our lightweight foundation models, craft applications in the hyperspectral domain using CORSA features and tackle the mid- and long-infrared wavelengths for both compression and AI-based applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Jiang, “Image compression with neural networks—a survey,” *Signal processing: image Communication*, vol. 14, no. 9, 1999, pp. 737–760
- [2] K. Gregor, F. Besse, D. Jimenez Rezende, I. Danihelka, and D. Wierstra, “Towards conceptual compression,” *Advances In Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 29, 2016, pp. 3549– 3557
- [3] Spiral Blue, “Spiral Blue Receives First Operational Data from Space Edge Computer Mission”, blog post: <https://www.spiralblue.space/post/spiral-blue-receives-first-operational-data-from-space-edge-computer-mission>
- [4] B. Beusen, X. Ivashkovych and T. V. Achteren, “Image Compression using Vector-Quantized Auto-Encoders with semantically meaningful feature extraction”, *4S Symposium 2022*, May 2022.
- [5] A. Razavi, A. v. d. Oord and O. Vinyals, “Generating Diverse High-Fidelity Images with VQ-VAE-2, *NeurIPS 2019*, June 2019.
- [6] B. Beusen, X. Ivashkovych, A. Luyts and T. V. Achteren, “On-Board Hyperspectral Image Compression Using Vector-Quantized Auto Encoders”, *IGARSS 2024*, July 2024.
- [7] X. Ivashkovych, L. Landuyt and T. V. Achteren, “CORSA Deep Earth Observation Semantic Compression applied to Flood Detection”, *OBPDC 2022*, September 2022.
- [8] B. Beusen, A. Luyts, X. Ivashkovych and T. V. Achteren “Lightweight and Efficient: A Family of Multimodal Earth Observation Foundation Models”, *IGARSS 2024*, July 2024.
- [9] M. H. P. Fuchs and B. Demir, “HySpecNet-11k: A Large-Scale Hyperspectral Dataset for Benchmarking Learning-Based Hyperspectral Image Compression Methods”, *IGARSS 2023*, June 2023.
- [10] CCSDS 123.0-b-2 & CCSDS 121.0-b-3, <https://www.connectbycnes.fr/ccsds-1230-b-2-ccsds-1210-b-3>
- [11] trtexec tool for TensorRT, <https://github.com/NVIDIA/TensorRT/tree/main/samples/trtexec>

- [12] JetPack SDK v6.0, <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetpack>
- [13] M. Makarenko, A. Burguete-Lopez, Q. Wang, S. Giancola, B. Ghanem, L. Passone and A. Fratolocchi, “Hardware-accelerated integrated optoelectronic platform towards real-time high-resolution hyperspectral video understanding”, *Nature Communications*, August 2024.
- [14] H. Yang, Y. Liang, X. Guo, L. Wu and Z. Wang, “Pruning Before Training May Improve Generalization, Provably”, January 2023.